

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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- 08.00.01 Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
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O'ZBEKISTON HUDUDLARIDA TURIZM TURLARINI RIVOJLANISH ORQALI BANDLIK DARAJASINI OSHIRISH

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TDIU huzuridagi "O'zbekiston iqtisodiyotini rivojlantirishning ilmiy asoslari va muammolari" ilmiy-tadqiqot markazi doktoranti

Abstract: In this article, the impact of the development of the tourism industry on the level of employment and the problems in the development of tourism types.

Key words: tourism infrastructure, employment, unemployment, ecotourism, cultural tourism, cluster system, economy, demographic factors.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada hududlarda turizm sohasining rivojlanishining aholi bandlik darajasiga ta'siri hamda turizm turlarini rivojlantirishdagi dolzarb muammolar haqida yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: turizm infratuzilmasi, bandlik, ishsizlik, ekoturizm, madaniy turizm, klaster tizimi, iqtisodiyot, demografik omillar.

Аннотация: В данной статье описано влияние развития туризма в регионах на уровень занятости населения и текущие проблемы развития туризма.

Ключевые слова: туристическая инфраструктура, занятость, безработица, экотуризм, культурный туризм, кластерная система, экономика, демографические факторы.

INTRODUCTION

In today's world, tourism is becoming one of the leading sector to improve the economy. Therefore, a number of positive changes are being made in the society aimed at creating new types of jobs for both men and women. As well as, a number of laws, decisions and decrees are being adopted for the purpose of developing the tourism sector. In particular, the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated, 05.01.2019, with PF-5611 on additional measures for the rapid development of tourism in the Republic of Uzbekistan was adopted ^[1]. Accordingly, comprehensive measures for the development of tourism in the country as one of the strategic sectors that ensure the diversification of the national economy, the rapid development of regions, the creation of new jobs, the increase of incomes and living standards of the population, and the increase of the country's investment attractiveness are phased. In addition, the problems related to tourism industry were also emphasized that there is a lack of accommodation facilities and infrastructure facilities, especially during the tourism season, insufficient coordination of the system of transporting passengers in different modes of transport, low level of organization of providing tourists with information about the existing tourism potential in the regions, ineffectiveness of marketing campaigns to promote tourism cultural heritage objects in the regions of the country and based on this, the following tasks were determined:

- implementation of international norms and standards which aimed at improving the regulatory framework in the field of tourism and creating favorable conditions for the development of tourism;
- development of tourism infrastructure and creation of an acceptable and comfortable tourism environment;
- development of transport logistics, expansion of internal and external routes, improving the quality of transport services;
- developing inner(local) tourism, which provides stimulation of activity of tourism activity subjects aimed at meeting the need for tourism services within the republic.

It is possible to increase the volume of GLP(YaHM) that tourism brings to the country's economy by developing the tourism types such as: cultural tourism, ecotourism, gastronomic tourism and others in the regions, as well as, increase the level of employment working in tourism sector of the population. According to statistics, eight out of ten people are busy with tourism sector in the USA, however this figure is very low in Uzbekistan. In order to improve infrastructure and employment in tourism industry, we, tourism experts, should make a great strain together.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS

A number of foreign and Uzbek scientists have been contributing to the development of tourism infrastructure and types of tourism in the regions.

In particular, R.I. Wolfe, who made a significant contribution to the formation of the approach to tourism as tourism, as well as the scientific works of North American scientists such as S.L. Smith, L.S. Michel, regional location of tourism system reaction resources, travel directions, territorial location of tourism system reaction resources, travel directions important aspects such as roads and transport links are explored. The first introduction to the field of tourism as a concept of tourism, belongs to S.A. Gann who stated that the tourism system consists of five interconnected complex elements: tourists, attractive resources, transport, service facilities and information routes ^[2]. According to the researcher S. Koper, the success of certain destinations not only increases the attractiveness of the products and services of the tourism system, but also the tourism as a whole. The strengthening of the destination in the minds of tourists, creating a new positive image depends on the development of the country's tourism system. In turn, the tourism system and cultural-historical features of the country increase the unique attractiveness of the destination ^[3].

According to A. J. Burkart and S. Medhlik, it is not possible to accurately and directly determine the impact of tourism on employment ^[4] and the reason for this is explained as follows:

- many of those employed in tourist destinations work in the same or similar positions that are not related to tourism and are indistinguishable from those there. For example, official statistics provide employment in residential buildings, restaurants and other food-related facilities, and in various modes of transport, which do not include tourism-related employment.

According to Uzbek scientists, in the A.A. Eshtayev's article entitled: "Influence of global trends on the development of tourism in Uzbekistan" describes the potential of tourism in our country and the global trends affecting its development. In addition, in order to reduce the level of unemployment in the country, analyzes were carried out in the case where the experience of the employment level in the field of tourism was studied in various developed countries ^[5].

According to the research done by B.B.Sobirov, an effective mechanism for increasing the competitiveness of a certain tourist area is the use of the cluster method in the organization of special tourist economic zones and their development ^[6]. If we conclude from this idea, if we use the system of tourism clusters in the regions, it is possible to achieve general tourism development by combining types of tourism.

METHODOLOGY

The research used the methods of analysis and synthesis of knowledge, generalization, social survey, comparative statistical analysis, as well as the principles of historicity, interrelationship and systematicity.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

There is a worldwide trend of increasing interest in cultural tourism products, and the World Tourism Organization predicts that the cultural tourism market will be one of the five leading segments of the tourism market in the future ^[7]. Local culture is an important feature of a tourist destination, and thanks to tourism, it becomes a flywheel of social and economic development. Cultural tourism is focused on cultural attractions and activities as the main reasons for traveling, and the participation of cultural tourism in all tourist movements is increasing. Thus, in France, Italy, Spain, the United Kingdom, income from tourists whose primary goal is to get acquainted with cultural goods and cultural achievements exceed 1/3 of total tourism revenues. It is no exaggeration to mention the cultural monuments of Uzbekistan among the countries mentioned above, which are known to the world for their cultural heritage monuments. As we know, today 4 architectural complexes are included in the UNESCO Representative List of World Heritage Sites - the Ichan Castle Museum-Reserve in Khiva (1990), the historical center of Bukhara (1993), the historical center of Samarkand "Samarkand - crossroads of cultures" (2001), the historical center of Shahrisabz, as well as the Ugam-Chotkal National Park (2016) and 9 intangible

heritage sites^[8]. Since the independence of Uzbekistan, great attention has been paid not only to the preservation of cultural heritage through the restoration of monuments, but also to the strengthening of national identity and recognition in world culture. According to the UNWTO report, “one job in the core tourism industry creates about one and a half additional (indirect) jobs in the tourism-related economy”. Moreover, “there are three workers indirectly dependent on each person working in hotels, such as travel agency staff, guides, taxi and bus drivers, food and beverage suppliers, laundry workers, textile workers, gardeners, shop staff for souvenirs and others, as well as airport employees”^[9].

Graph 1: Indicators of positive change in the field of tourism in the territory of Uzbekistan for seven years

Indicators	2017	2023
Number of tourists	2,7 million	4,3 million (during 9 months of 2023)
Placement number	767	5,5 thousand
Activities of tourist organizations and travel agents (number)	749	2 404
Guide-excursionist	574	2864
The average sum of money spent by each foreign tourist in the territory of the republic, excluding direct travel expenses	197 US dollars	1,72 billion dollars (during 9 months of 2023)
Number of local (inner) tourists	10.5 million	14,9 million

Source: created by the researcher based on statistical data
(<https://kun.uz/uz/news/>)

According to official data, the number of foreign tourists who came to Uzbekistan was 2.7 million in 2017, 5.2 million in 2022, and 4.3 million in the last 9 months of 2023. The average length of stay of tourists in our country is 4-5 days and has increased by 1.5 times compared to the corresponding period of last year (2023).

In 2017, the average amount of money spent by each foreign tourist in the territory of the republic, excluding direct travel expenses, was 197 US dollars, this figure reached 400 US dollars in 2023, and the volume of tourism exports in 9 months of 2023 was 1.72 billion dollar.

The number of local tourists also increased by 107% in 2023 compared to 2017 and reached 14.9 million people.

Positive results were also achieved during 5 years, new tourism directions were established, including the granting of the status of “Tourism Neighborhood”, “Tourism Village” and “Tourism Farm” to the citizens’ gatherings of the Republic with high tourism potential and mechanisms to support them were introduced. During 2022, the tourism village of “Sentob” in Nurota district of Navoi region and the villages of “Ertosh-soy” and “Ovjazsoy” in Ohangaron district of Tashkent region were given the status of “Tourism village”. As a result of the establishment of 90 family guest houses and 20 types of services in these villages, about 400 villagers were employed. Interestingly, UNWTO recognized Uzbekistan as the 4th among the 20 countries with the fastest developing tourism sector^[9].

If we look at the statistics, the number of tourists visiting our country is increasing (an estimated 6.6 million in 2023) again after the pandemic situation. If this positive situation continues, it will also increase our tourism opportunities. It is necessary to develop a program for the wide development of the service sector integrated into the tourism network in the regions, and create jobs in the tourism sector in the regions, so that people who have not yet experienced this industry and improve their skills. Of course, it will be appropriate, if favorable conditions are created.

According to the official statistics given by WTTC; Oxford Economics, number of travel and tourism jobs worldwide increased gradually from 2019 to 2022, also, they are forecasted till 2033 and these indications can be seen clearly in the graph.

Graphical data shows that employment rates in the tourism sector worldwide are increasing in high numbers. In turn, we can say that this is a positive indicator for Uzbekistan, because each tourist visiting our tourism country can use at least 11 services, which certainly affects the level of labor resources in the field of tourism.

In the development of tourism types in the regions, we can use the tourism cluster model system. But unfortunately, this system has not yet been implemented in our country. If we pay attention to the economy of developed countries, they are using tourism clusters. Due to this system, several sectors of tourism in the regions of the country are united in the form of a single system, contributing to the development of the tourism industry and increasing the level of employment. It should be noted that creation of tourism cluster in the regions can develop the types of tourism, increase the competitiveness of the regions and create new jobs.

Graph 2: Number of travel and tourism jobs worldwide from 2019 to 2022, with a forecast for 2033(in million)

Source: created by the researcher based on statistical data by WTTC; Oxford Economics.

Clustering is the geographic connection of interdependent actors (businesses, institutions and organizations that support them), who operate in the same industry, participate in the same value chain, collaborate and compete with one another and have business ties. According to Harvard Business School, more than 32% of employment in the US economy is provided by clusters. It should be noted that the level of labor productivity and wages in clusters are much higher than the average indicator of the country. In the USA, goods and services are exported outside the region in production sectors organized on the basis of the cluster principle, and wages are 29% higher than the average indicator [10]. The experience of many countries in the field of tourism shows that clusters make it possible for the economy to achieve high efficiency, thereby ensuring the development of the nation and increase the well-being of the population. The formation of clusters makes it possible to make fuller use of tourism resources available in the country. The formation of a tourism cluster within any region is an important way to find a solution to problems related to the development of the industry.

In order to gain an understanding of the cluster system, it is important to pay attention this “Clustering is a group of enterprises connected to a chain under a single management, concentrated in one geographical area and aimed at solving a certain specific task which are connected with each other and combine their labor forces in order to strengthen collective competition”. It is an integrative, innovative and, of course, science-based process that can ensure economic growth.

In the monograph “Tourism potential of Uzbekistan and its development prospects” written by A.A. Esh-tayev, a model of the organization of a tourism cluster dedicated to the development of the tourism sector in Uzbekistan and improving the ways of increasing competitiveness in the regions was recommended [11].

The formation of a tourism cluster within any region is an important solution to the problems related to the development of the sector. Three main reasons for territorial concentration of business entities in the field of tourism in regions are indicated:

1. The possibility of obtaining economic benefits by taking into account the costs to ensure the use of existing tourism resources in regions in the process of creating a tourism product, implementing it and using it, as well as following the tourism chain;
2. The unique territorial proximity of the location of tourism resources that create tourism conditions in the region in order to form lower tariffs for tourist and recreational services and ensure their provision in shorter periods;
3. Formation of unique information resources in the process of socio-economic cooperation between business entities located in a certain area, including in the field of social communications, training of the workforce necessary for tourism activities and the application of effective technologies in their use creation of a single information base.

Yashil IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

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